

**MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN LONG TUBULAR BONES AFTER
EXPERIMENTAL OSTEOPOROSIS IN RATS**

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Introduction. *The gastrointestinal tract is a part of the system that participates in the metabolism of minerals, which are considered components of bone tissue. In diseases of the brain, the absorption of mineral substances and vitamins (including calcium and vitamin D) is disrupted. This leads to a decrease in the amount of calcium in bone tissue and a decrease in the mineral density of bone tissue – osteoporosis. After resection of the stomach in hospitals, in most patients there are serious violations of the digestive process, a decrease in body weight and the appearance of severe clinical manifestations of a number of diseases.*

Keywords. *Experiment, osteoporosis, bone tissue, gastric resection, morphometry.*

The purpose of the work. To investigate the morphofunctional state of bone tissue in experimental osteoporosis after resection of experimental rats by Bilrot - II method.

Material and methods: 27 simple white male rats weighing 170-200 gr were selected to conduct the experiment. 12 rats were allocated to the first control group. 15 rats were allocated to the second experimental group and their results were analyzed.

Results. The living weight of animals was analyzed for 3 months. From the 7th day after the operation, the weight of the rats was reduced until the end of the experiment. The fact that rats in the experimental group consumed less food than rats in the control group, it was found that their wool lost its natural luster and became less mobile.

Live weight of rats in the continuation of the experiment, (M ±m)

The measured period of weight of rats	Group of rats	
	Control, n = 12	Bilrot-II, n = 15
7 days	200,27 ± 1,69	191,13 ± 1,83*
30 days	228,44 ± 1,82	204,73 ± 2,11**
60 days	240,55 ± 1,80	219,80 ± 2,12**
90 days	258,00 ± 1,93	232,00 ± 2,07**
Note: the reliability of the control group * - p < 0,05; ** - p < 0,001		

One of the possible problems caused by osteoporosis is observed in the thigh bone. Therefore, in both groups of rats in the experiment, morphometric indicators of the thigh bone were studied and, accordingly, the following data were obtained: bone weight - (563,83 ± 4,22) and (506,95 ± 4,53) mg; bone length - (35,98 ± 0,26) and (32,38 ± 0,28) mm; width of the proximal epiphysis section - (7,55 ± 0,05) and (6,78 ± 0,06) mm; width of

the distal epiphysis section - $(6,48 \pm 0,04)$ and $(5,84 \pm 0,05)$ mm; width of the diaphysis section - $(3,64 \pm 0,02)$ and $(3,27 \pm 0,02)$ mm; front-rear dimension of the diaphysis section - $(3,54 \pm 0,02)$ and $(3,18 \pm 0,02)$ mm. There was a significant decrease in all indicators of operated rats compared to those of the control group ($p < 0,001$).

Conclusion. Thus, after resection of the test animals by the Bilrot -ii method, a violation of the digestive process was observed. This was manifested by a decrease in body weight. As a result of the data we have obtained based on the experience we have conducted and comparing them with the data from a number of clinical literature, we concluded that resection of the femur by the Bilrot method leads to morphofunctional changes in the structure of bone tissue in experimental animals, that is, changes in osteomorphometric indicators and architectonics.

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